

A Study on Effect of Depression on Quality of Life in Post-Menopausal WomenAkhila Sabbavarapu¹, Nimidithalli Annapurna², Shaik Noor Ahammad³, P. Suseela Kumari⁴, T Jaya Chandra⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram.²Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram.³Post graduate, Department of Psychiatry, GSL Medical College, Rajamahendravaram.⁴Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram.⁵Professor, Department of Microbiology, GSL Medical College, Rajamahendravaram

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Introduction:** Menopause is a crucial physiological process in women's lives here depression is one the psychological condition. A study was conducted to assess the severity of depression in post-menopausal women (PMW).**Methods:** It was a cross sectional study conducted in the department of Psychiatry, GSL Medical College, conducted between November 2018 and March 2020. The PMW attended psychiatry department on OPD basis, met ICD 10 criteria for depression were considered, those with other psychiatric disorders, chronic physical illness were not considered. The study population were thoroughly explained the purpose of the study and informed consent was obtained. For all the eligible study participants, socio-demographic and clinical information was recorded. Hamilton depression Rating (HAM D) scale was applied to assess the severity of depression and utian quality of life (UQOL) scale was used to assess the QOL. Chi square test was used, P <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.**Results:** Total 120 PMW were included, the mean age was 48.13 ± 4.74 years. Out of the 40 (100%) PMW with depression, total QOL wise, 65% (26) were in 48 – 60 group followed by 35% (14) in 61 – 74 group. Whereas in the UQOL group, the total QOL was 75 to 87 in 47.5% (19) and 88 to 100 in 52.5% (21) of study members; statistically there was significant association.**Conclusion:** Depression is also one of the commonest psychological disorder among the PMW. No assessment of severity of depression, small sample size are the limitations of this research.**Keywords:** Women, Depression, Psychiatry, Scale.

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Introduction

Menopause is a crucial physiological process in women's lives where several physiological and biological changes can takes place. [1] Due to this women exhibit several clinical symptoms because of hormonal, physical and psychological changes in their body [2] Anxiety, mood swings, depression and stress are some common psychological symptoms in women at menopause. [3]

Depression is a psychological state where there is loss of interest in routine life. The reported prevalence of depression is two times higher among the female. [4] In women it is associated with reproductive events termed as reproductive associated syndrome. In postpartum and perimenopausal period, there is high incidence of depression. [2] This entire scenario is due to the hormonal changes in the luteal phase of cycles.

Several studies have been reported throughout the globe regarding depression and menopause. [2] Health is the important aspect to lead a better quality of life (QOL). The impact of depends menopause on the QOL is the consequence of physical, social and also mental changes. In one of our previous reports it was concluded that anxiety is one of the commonest psychological disorder among the post-menopausal women (PMW). [5] With these a study was conducted to assess the severity of depression in PMW.

Methods

It was a cross sectional study conducted in the department of Psychiatry, GSL Medical College, Rajamahendravaram. Study was conducted between November 2018 and March 2020. Study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

An informed written consent was taken from the study members.

The PMW attended psychiatry department on OPD basis and met the ICD 10 criteria for depression disorder were considered in this research. Individuals with other psychiatric disorders, chronic physical illness and other comorbid substance dependence and non-cooperative members were not considered in this research. The study members were divided into test and control groups. Those were diagnosed to have psychiatric disorder were included in the test and normal women were included in the control group.

Semi-structured proforma was used in this research. The study population were thoroughly explained the purpose of the study and informed consent was obtained. For all the eligible study participants, socio-demographic and clinical information was recorded with the help of a pre-tested proforma. Hamilton depression Rating (HAM D) scale was applied to assess the severity of depression [6] and utian quality of life (UQOL) scale was used to assess the QOL. [7]

Table 1: Comparison of study participants based on total QOL in depression group and UQOL scale group; n (%)

Total QOL	Anxiety	UQOL	Total
48 to 60	26 (65)	0	26 (32.5)
61 to 74	14 (35)	0	14 (17.5)
75 to 87	0	19 (47.5)	19 (47.5)
88 to 100	0	21 (52.5)	21 (52.5)
Total	40 (100)	40 (100)	80 (100)
Statistical analysis	$\Psi^2 = 72.76; P > 0.01$. Statistically significant		

Discussion

Globally, depression is leading cause of psychological disorder with high mortality and morbidity. [6, 9] Currently the diagnosed depression is confirmed by standard interview method and assessment scale. HAM D 17 is most commonly used to estimate the severity and treatment response those were already diagnosed with depression disorder. [10] Just 20 – 30 mnts time period is required to complete HAM D to each patients. [11] Whereas in this research, 21 mnts was the average time period required for each participant to analyze with HAM D scale.

The mean age of the study participant was mean age was 48.13 ± 4.74 whereas the mean age was 46.22 ± 4.24 years those were diagnosed to have depression disorder. The mean age was reported to be 48.35 ± 5.42 years. [10] In this research the incidence of depression was 33.3% among the PMW. It was reported to be 39.2% in another research. [11] As per this depression was found to be one of the common psychological disorder among PMW. In a study reported by Afshari *et al.* the prevalence of depression among the PMW was 59.8%; of this

Sample Size Calculation: Sample size was calculated using formulae $n = 4pq/l^2$. Here prevalence (p) was taken at 80% as per the study by. [8] $Q = 100 - P$; $100 - 80 = 20$. Error was taken at the rate of 10% of P. When these were included, the sample size was considered to be 120.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analyzed using SPSS software version 20. Chi square test was used for the statistical analysis; $P < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

Total 120 PMW were included in this research. The mean age was 48.13 ± 4.74 years. With HAM D scale was applied on the study members, 40 found diagnosed have depression disorder. Out of the 40 (100%) PMW with depression, total QOL wise, 65% (26) were in 48 – 60 group followed by 35% (14) in 61 – 74 group. Whereas in the UQOL group, the total QOL was 75 to 87 in 47.5% (19) and 88 to 100 in 52.5% (21) of study members; statistically there was significant association (Table 1).

39.8% women had mild and 16% had moderate depression. [12]

In the present study, the prevalence of depression was detected to be more in lower socioeconomic status compared to the higher socioeconomic group. It was consistent with a study conducted in Beijing city by Li *et al.*, where the association was found between depression in postmenopausal women and socioeconomic status. [13] In the current research statistically there was significant difference in the QOL and depression (Table 1). Whereas the early PMW have to face more psychological problems such as depression compare to others. [14]

Conclusion

Depression is also one of the commonest psychological disorder among the PMW. Non assessment of severity of depression, small sample size are the limitations of this research.

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